

EARTH SCIENCES

THREE-DIMENSIONAL SURFACE LASER SCANNING TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

The integration of digital techniques with geodetic and photogrammetric technology has led to the creation of new tools for collecting spatial information about the terrain - the terrestrial laser location system or terrestrial laser scanner (YLS).

Keywords: Terrestrial laser scanners, laser rangefinder and laser beams, raster image

The main essence of terrestrial laser scanning is to measure the distances from the scanner to the points of the object with high accuracy and record the corresponding directions (vertical and horizontal angles). At this time, the measured quantities of ground laser scanners are similar to those of electronic tachymeters. But the general principle of capturing the object (not from individual points) is described by surface laser scanners (YLS), the result of the work is obtained as a three-dimensional view.

Images obtained by YLS are usually multiple in some cases. It carries multi-memory data, which takes up more space. Here, in terms of statistics, neighboring elements of the image repeat each other [1]. The main system for terrestrial laser scanners consists of YLS and a computer with special software. YLS consists of a high-frequency adaptive laser rangefinder and a laser beam lubricator.

The main function of the laser rangefinder in the terrestrial laser scanner is to use the pulse and phase methods, as well as the right angle method, when measuring distances.

YLS has a servo drive, polygonal mirror or prism as the drive head unit. The servo drive head ensures a given amount of beam on the horizontal surface, while the scanner head turns all the way to the top. The transformation on the vertical surface is due to the rotation of the mirror [4].

During the scanning process, the direction of propagation of the laser beam and the distance to the points of the object are recorded. As a result of YLS operation, raster images are obtained (Fig. 1), the value of a pixel is determined by a vector with the following components: the measured distance, the intensity of the reflected signal, and the RGB component characterizing the real color of the point. As a result, the position (row and column) of each element (pixel) of the raster reflects the values of the measured vertical and horizontal angles. For most YLS models, the true color characteristics for each dot are obtained using a non-metric digital camera.

Figure 1. The result from the laser scanner - raster image

Another form of presentation of results of YLS is presented with five features: set of points of laser rays reflected from objects located in the field of view of scanners, that is, spatial coordinates (X, Y, Z), intensity and real color are indicated [2,3].

The spatial coordinates of the points of the object in the scanner's coordinate system are calculated according to the distances and beam direction obtained by the formulas used (Fig.2):

Figure 2. Location of angles in YLS

$$\begin{aligned} X &= R \cos \varphi \sin \theta \\ Y &= R \sin \varphi \cos \theta \\ Z &= R \cos \theta \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here, R is the measured distance from the scanner to the object; φ – horizontal angles of the measured direction; θ – vertical angles of the measured direction calculated from the Z axis to the direction vector, (the zenith distance of the direction).

Formulas (1) are conversion formulas from the polar coordinate system to the Cartesian coordinate system. For each scanner, these have a specific value, where the mismatch of the radiation source and angles, the eccentricities of the rotating vertical and horizontal flows of the device and other parameters called scanning calibration are taken into account.

The result. The laser scanning process is the fastest and most efficient way to obtain large-scale street and building site plans, profiles and cross-sections of road surfaces. Laser scanning is the most up-to-date, ef-

ficient and useful technology for obtaining more accurate and comprehensive digital information about the terrain, creating digital models of the earth's surface relief (RRM).

Literature

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